

The Organizing Committee of the Join Conferences HPC 2023 and
CMMSE 2023 CERTIFIES:

Mr. Gabriel Gomez Lopez

Has presented a seminar entitled:

**Building a hybrid network topology in an HPC Infiniband-based
cluster**

July 3, 2023

Sincerely,

CMMSE
INT CONFERENCE
ON COMPUTATIONAL
AND MATHEMATICAL METHODS
IN SCIENCE AND
ENGINEERING